

INTEGRATED METHODS OF TEACHING LISTENING AND SPEAKING

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ABSTRACT

This article helps to understand that a serious approach to listening learning, careful planning of words, tasks and forms of control, should take into account the factor of language and speech preparation of students.

In today's fast-paced world, science and technology are also growing rapidly. Development in every field is moving forward. In particular, great changes are taking place in science. Delivering each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education.

As a type, reading in a foreign language as a form of speech activity and indirect communication is, in the opinion of many researchers, the most necessary for most people. The ability to communicate directly with native speakers, as a rule, is relatively low, the ability to read in a foreign language - almost everything. Therefore, teaching reading plays a dominant role in the target.

The process of reading and its outcome - the acquisition of information - is of great importance in people's communicative and social activities. This form of written communication provides the transmission of experience accumulated by humanity,

different areas of life, develops intelligence, sharpens emotions, that is, teaches, develops, nurtures. In short, reading shapes the qualities of the most advanced and socially valuable person.

In the process of globalization, it is hard to imagine our lives without the internet. It is one of the most effective ways to learn and use a foreign language. You will be able to communicate with foreign speakers through the Internet. Writing exercises can be improved by writing a letter via e-mail.

A foreign language is just a grammar rule taught in courses. Any language is more of a means of communication, verbal communication. Speaking English is the best example. In conversations with strangers, you don't need changing vowels, and verb forms may be ignored. But the ability to perceive speech by ear, understand the interlocutors, and speak clearly and fluently will be required. To this end, language classes include special classes with "native speakers", extracurricular activities for

communication, and even separate conversations.

The first thing you need to do before learning to speak English is to learn to listen to a foreign speaker. It is very difficult to do this completely without outside help, but we will try. For this purpose, freely accessible audio materials and your own sound are perfect. But first things first.

Listen to songs in English - it can be done at any time, at the same time as anything else. Even if English compositions appear in the background while driving, cleaning, washing dishes, or just walking, you will learn the sound of words, the rhythm of speech, the intonations of English.

Radio stations and podcasts with relevant news provide interesting information and are taught to listen and understand spoken English. You can listen to the radio like music at any time of the day or night, combining business with pleasure.

This listening is suitable for more advanced students because the artistic texts are much more complex than the songs. But audio books are read well by professional actors who speak clearly and fluently.

Your task at this stage is to listen to natural English and try to repeat it as accurately as possible. Compare the sample version to your own. Pay attention to sounds, intonations, speech speed. Make a summary and new notes, and each time your pronunciation will be closer to the original. The advantage of this method is that, in addition to analytical perception and repetition, the "imitation" mechanism introduced into the brain is activated. Even completely unfamiliar sounds are recognizable and easy to observe.

There are many ways to exercise the speech apparatus. But how easy and fun it

can be depends directly on the method you choose. We offer you the most pleasant, entertaining and not difficult tricks:

Maybe this happens when you listen to English songs. Rhythmic music and bright hits "catch up" and encourage you to sing together. Don't restrain yourself, sing along with the performers. In the car, in the shower, in the kitchen. Don't be afraid to make mistakes, but notice and correct your mistakes every time.

Knowing all the difficulties will allow you to accurately assess the level of difficulty in listening, take them into account when organizing training listening, remove them and sometimes artificially create, bringing the lesson as close as possible to real communication situations.

The use of technology is useful in every aspect of foreign language learning (reading, writing, listening comprehension and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, it is impossible to do this process without a computer, player, CDs. Listening is one of the most important parts of language learning. This requires the student to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, grammatical rules, vocabulary, and meanings at the same time. The use of modern technologies in the educational process is also an important factor for students to be well acquainted with and use information and communication technologies. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most effective methods. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to videos, demonstrations, dialogues, movies or cartoons in a foreign language; - It is possible to listen and watch radio broadcasts in foreign languages and TV

programs; - use of tape recorders and methods; - CD players are available. cassettes, which are more traditional

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